

DETERMINATION OF RESOURCE INDICATORS OF PARTS AND UNITS OF LIMITING RELIABILITY OF AUTOMOBILE CRANE

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Abstract: In this article, we consider the importance of the durability characteristics of machines, their components and parts, which allows us to justify enterprises for the maintenance of machines and develop economically feasible technical specifications for operational repairs, i.e. for routine repairs of machines.

Determining the need for spare parts and operating materials, taking into account their reliability, also actively influences the operational characteristics of hoisting and transport machines.

Key words: maintenance, durability, hoisting and transport machines, reliability, limit state.

Introduction. To begin with, let's consider the definition of resource indicators of the reliability of automobile cranes that characterize their durability. To determine the 80% or 90% resource of parts and machine assemblies using a graphical method, it is necessary to determine a number of parameters that allow the calculation of the empirical resource distribution function F_{ej} , as well as the calculation of approximating yarn coefficients for drawing up graphic images of the distribution according to the accepted law (exponential or logarithmic).

Reliability theory studies the aging processes of machines, mechanisms, equipment, i.e. changes in their quality over time. Quality is characterized by corresponding indicators of operational properties.

Reliability is understood as the properties of a machine, unit or mechanism in the general case, an object, to perform specified functions, maintaining over time the established operational indicators within specified limits corresponding to the

specified modes and conditions of use, maintenance, repairs, storage and transportation.

Changes in the performance properties of machines, given data or during design and manufacture, are due to their interaction with factors characterizing operating conditions: load, speed, climate, etc.

The main concept of reliability theory is failure. Failure is understood as an event consisting in a malfunction of a machine (unit, assembly unit or system), i.e. a condition in which the machine is unable to perform specified functions with the parameters established (not capable of performing specified) by the requirements of technical documentation (standards, specifications, etc.).

To quantitatively characterize one or more properties that make up the reliability of a machine, reliability indicators are used. They can be single or complex. Single reliability indicators refer to one of the properties, and complex indicators refer to several properties that make up the reliability of the machine.

Failure-free properties are quantified by the following single indicators: probability of failure-free operation, average time between failures, failure rate, failure flow parameter. Running time is the duration or volume of operation of a machine.

The most important indicator of the durability property is the technical resource - the operating time of the machine from the start of operation or its resumption after a major overhaul until the onset of the limit state.

A limit state is a state of a machine in which its further operation must be terminated due to an irreparable violation of safety requirements, irreparable failure to comply with the specified established requirements of technical documentation (standards, technical, etc.).

The durability property is also assessed by gamma - percentage life, average life between major repairs, average life before write-off.

Operability is understood as the state of a machine in which it is able to perform specified functions while maintaining specified parameters within the limits

established by regulatory and technical documentation. Failure or significant damage disrupts the operational state.

The resulting operating time or the so-called resource of this part of a hydraulically driven truck crane operating in hot climates is significantly lower than that of truck cranes used in temperate operating zones.

Material and methods. Next, we consider determining the 80% and 90% service life of the bearing cage of the cargo winch of the KS-5572 truck crane. Determination of the empirical distribution function for the bearing life of the holder of the cargo winch of the KS-5572 truck crane.

Table 1.

№	Operating time, resource (motor hour)	r_i	n_i	N_i	$N + 1 - m_{i-1}$	$N + 1 - N_i$	Δ_i	m_i	$F_{\%j}$
1	915		1					1	0.09
2	1298	1							
3	1887		1	2	10	9	1.11	2.11	0.191
4	2417		1	3			1.11	3.22	0.292
5	2607		1	4			1.11	4.33	0.393
6	2789	1					1.42	5.75	0.523
7	2830		1	6	5.67	4			
8	2963	1							
9	3076	1							
10	3326		1	9	4.25	1	4.25	10.0	0.909

Certain values of the empirical distribution function of the race bearing life

and other parameters for determining the life are presented in table. 1. Thus, for each value of operating time (resource), we calculate the corresponding value of the distribution function.

Next, based on the obtained calculation results, we will construct a graph of the dependence of the function $F_{3j} = f(T_{nar})$ to determine the gamma-percentage life of the bearing of the cargo winch cage of the KS-5572 automobile crane, which is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Determination of the 80% life of the main race bearing winches for truck crane brand KS-5572.

Conclusion.. From figure 1 it can be seen that the 80% service life of the bearing cage of the cargo winch of the KS-5572 brand truck crane in the hot climate of the Republic of Uzbekistan is $\gamma_{80} = 1995$ machine-hour or $\gamma_{80} = 4433.3$ machine-hour, and 90% the resource is $\gamma_{90} = 945$ machine-hour or $\gamma_{90} = 2100,0$ machine-hour.

These service life values for the cage bearing are significantly lower than those of truck-mounted cranes used in moderate operating zones.

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